

ISic3541

Fragment of a Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

via S. Marta, fondo Martines

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3631

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 26 cm

Width 17 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 40 mm

Lines 2-4: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [D(is)] M(anibus)
2. [---]ria
3. [---]as
4. [---]cis

Apparatus

Text from Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

to the shades of the underworld(?) ...

Translation (it)

agli dei Mani(?) ...

Commentary

It is a reasonable assumption that this is the upper right fragment of an epitaph, but certainty is not possible

Digital identifiers:

TM 284782

EDR 033627

EDCS 14805811

PHI 313676

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias 7*. Messina. At 44

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